

EFFECT OF DIVERSITY COMBINING IN MOBILE TERRESTRIAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

Mobile communications have experienced massive growth in recent years. It is also in high demand nowadays. However, these systems suffer from much impairment such as multipath propagation effects and thermal noise. The study investigates the effect of using Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) and Binary Differential Phase Shift Keying (BDPSK) with Maximal Ratio Combiner (MRC) which will improve the overall system performance better in mobile environment so that the transmitted signal can be retrieved at the receiver with minimum error. The effects of the mobile communication environment which hindered the transmitted signals were first studied.

The system model for processing the received signal at mobile speed of 30 km/h in two different channels; Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and mobile terrestrial channels was developed and simulated. Randomly produced data and water lilies image were used as source data which were gray encoded, processed by BPSK and BDPSK schemes, properly filtered by square root raised cosine filter. These signals were then passed through the mobile multipath Rayleigh environment and AWGN. Then at the receiver, MRC combined two strong paths to evaluate the performances which were measured in term of Average Bit Error Rate (BER) and image quality. The simulation was carried out using MATLAB 7.4 application package.

The results show that the performance of BDPSK signaling scheme was found to be better than BPSK scheme giving lower Average BER indicating lower erroneous bits at the same point when transmitting the same number of bits. Moreover, the received image quality was also in agreement with the performance when randomly produced source data was used.

In mobile communication, good quality of service is the major concern, because it changes business more than anything else and the system suffers from impairment. Adoption of fade margin or continue increasing the transmitted power is also inefficient. Hence modulation with diversity is essential. In line with this, the results indicate that modulation schemes are quite effective in combating channel impairment and can be used as references for the design of new reduced error system.

KEYWORDS - Mobile terrestrial, Maximal-Ratio Combiner, Average BER, random noise, image quality

INTRODUCTION

In mobile communications, the signal is degraded by terrestrial multipath fading in the lower atmosphere known as troposphere (Pornchai *et al.*, 2009) This troposphere is between altitude of 0 and 70 km and consists of many objects such as buildings, mountains, trees, moving cars, sign posts at the ground surface and natural phenomena like temperature, humidity, rainfall, etc at above the ground surface. These artificial and natural phenomena obstruct the transmitted signal, hindered the signal to reflect, refract, diffract and scatter, and move in different paths called multipath propagation causing the received signal to be degraded. The different paths add up constructively when the received signal paths are in phase and destructively under unfavourable phase conditions. The effects of terrestrial multipath propagation are signal fading, delay spread which is very dominant in urban environment leading to intersymbol interference (ISI) distortion, and lastly the doppler spread which occurs when there is relative motion in terrestrial environment. Therefore, these result in signal fluctuation at the receiver (Raji and Adeyemo, 2009).

There are many techniques to address this fading issue, such as Rake receiver, MIMO, OFDM and etc. However, it may be still necessary to remove the amplitude and phase shift caused by the channel (Zhifeng, 2007). In this paper, at the receiver, two different propagation paths were selected in terms of their Average Power. The received paths were multiplied by the conjugate of the channel impulse response of the corresponding paths to eliminate the effect of phase and then add up to obtain the weighted sum (Flavio and Michael, 2009; Ramesh *et al.*,2007). This new technique is known as power selection MRC. This is different from ordinary MRC method where all the available paths were combined.

A wireless communication simulators which include random data generator and image data source, gray coding, modulations, two different channel models; Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) and multipath terrestrial models, MRC demodulation and filtering using square root raised cosine pulse shaping filter were built. The effect of the two channel models to the randomly produced data and image data source in the transmitter with constellation and Average BER plots under BPSK and BDPSK modulations were observed. Gray coding was adopted after source data to avoid smearing together of successive symbols known as intersymbol interference (ISI) distortion at the receiving end. AWGN otherwise referred to as thermal noise here, was used as reference channel because it has flat power spectral density at all frequencies while multipath terrestrial channel has an impulse response which is multiplicative.

The impulse response depends on the time and delay indicating different values of amplitude and phases as the channel varies (Rappaport, 2002). After the high signal power selection MRC, demodulation was carried out to convert the radio frequency (RF) back to baseband and properly filtered by square root raised cosine pulse shaping filter with a roll-off factor of 0.25 to carry out the conversion from analog to digital and band-limit the signal. The bit errors were obtained in the transmission of randomly produced data, and the ratio of these erroneous bits to the transmitted bits were computed and averaged over certain number of iterations.

For image data source, the received image quality over two modulation schemes was compared to original image in the two channels. Since terrestrial environment consists of both artificial and natural factors which different from place to place, it would be very hard to embark on field measurements despite the fact that it would not give useful feedback (Ramjee and Hiroshima, 2002). Experimental approach is also expensive and not available, based on this, simulation based approach with Matlab 7.4 application package was adopted which is widely acceptable throughout the world in the paper.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Since the behavior of the mobile terrestrial channels strongly depends on the environment such as terrain, foliage, buildings and other moving objects like cars, it will be very hard to reproduce field test because such approach would not provide useful feedback in the early stage of design. Therefore, a simulation based approach is preferred to study the effects of this channel condition with MATLAB 7.4 application package using the developed algorithms. The system model was simulated and evaluated at mobile speed of 30 km/h using the developed algorithms.

SYSTEM AND CHANNEL MODELS

In this paper, a wireless communication simulator including gray coding, BPSK and BDPSK schemes, AWGN and fast, flat fading channels with two paths, MRC, demodulator and filter was developed. These are all shown in Figure 1 and achieved using the in-built functions of MATLAB 7.4 application package.

Figure 1: System model

The received signal $x(t)$ through the AWGN channel can be expressed as

$$x(t) = S_{BPSK,BDPSK}(t) + n(t); \quad (1)$$

while the received signal $x_l(t)$, on the L^{th} diversity branch, assuming fast and flat fading with different fading loss over each symbol interval, can be expressed by Proakis (2001) as :

$$x_l(t) = \alpha_l(t, \tau) S_{BPSK,BDPSK}(t) + n_l(t); \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (2)$$

where $S(t)$ is the BPSK, BDPSK transmitted signals,
 $\alpha_l(t)$ is the complex fading coefficient at time t , and delay τ ,
 $n_l(t)$ denotes the complex AWGN with zero mean and variance N_0 in each branch.

For MRC diversity receiver,
 The weighted sum of $x_l(t)$ is expressed by (Pornchai et al., 2009; Flavio and Michael, 2009) as

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=1}^L \omega_i x_i(t) \quad (3)$$

where $\omega_i = \alpha_i^*(t, \tau)$ is the weight of the i^{th} branch.

The complex coefficient of the terrestrial fading, $\alpha_{ter,i}(t, \tau)$ of the i^{th} branch can be expressed by Rappaport (2002) as:

$$\alpha_i(t, \tau) = a_i(t, \tau) \exp(j\phi_{ter,i}(t, \tau)) + b_{ter,i}(t, \tau) \quad (4)$$

where $a_{ter,i}$ is the associated amplitude at time t , and delay τ ;

$\phi_{ter, l}$ is assumed to be uniformly distributed over $[-\pi, \pi]$

$b_{ter, l}(t, \tau)$ is complex Gaussian random process with power spectral density $2\sigma_{ter, l}^2$.

In this paper, fast fading channel for both flat fading which represents mobile terrestrial and AWGN channels was modeled, so the two different environments were simulated as described.

A model simulated to GSM was chosen, where the carrier frequency was 900 MHz, and bandwidth of each channel was 200 Hz. The speed 'v' of the mobile unit simulated was 30 km/h. the maximum Doppler spread, f_d , is given by (Rappaport, 2002; Gayatri and Mohana, 2002) as:

$$f_d = \frac{vf}{c} \quad (5)$$

where v = speed of the mobile unit

f = carrier frequency

c = speed of light

Using the above simulation parameters contained in Table 1, f_d was calculated to be 25Hz.

Therefore the estimate for the coherence time T_{ch} which is the reciprocal of the maximum Doppler spread was obtained to be 40 ms.

This value is smaller than the assumed slot length of 50 ms indicating the fast fading channel.

From the simulation parameters, the maximum delay spread τ_m was 200 ns.

Therefore, the corresponding coherence bandwidth ' B_c ' is

$$B_c = \frac{1}{200ns} = 5MHz$$

The obtained value is larger than the assumed bandwidth of 200 Hz indicating frequency non-selective fading or flat fading.

Source Data and Parameters

The simulation supports two kinds of data source; randomly produced data and later an image file to validate the simulations results. Randomly produced data is ideal to test the BER performance and channel effect to signal constellation while image files give us an intuitive impression and comparison for different channels. The proposed model used BPSK and BDPSK modulation schemes to process the data source. The flow chart for MATLAB simulation is shown in Figure 2 while the simulation parameters conditions as fast fading are also contained in Table

1

Figure 2: Flowchart of MATLAB simulation

The random data was processed directly using the flowchart of Figure 2 while the image data was processed using the pseudocode below and the flowchart in Figure 2.

START

Obtain input image filename (e.g. 'name.jpeg')

Acquire the image

Display the image

Transform image to data suitable for transmission

{

convert the image matrix to a row vector, $V_{im} = 1 \times (\text{row} \times \text{column} \times \text{depth})$

encode the image vector V_{im} with respect to the modulation schemes

}

Feed the encoded image data (the symbols to be transmitted) into the system (MRC)

Obtain the output vector of the system (the received symbols)

Transform the output vector back into image

{

decode the symbols with respect to the modulation order

convert the vector into a matrix using the transmitted image dimension

}

Save the received image to disk

Display the received image

STOP

Pseudocode for Image Application

Table1: MRC simulation parameters

Parameter	Type
Fading	Terrestrial multipath Rayleigh
Modulation Scheme	BPSK, BDPSK
Carrier frequency	900 MHz
Bandwidth of signal	200 Hz
Delay spread	200 ns
Roll-off factor of filter	0.25
Noise	AWGN
Speed of mobile unit	30 km/h
Number of iterations	30 iterations

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained through the simulation studies for both randomly produced data and image sources in mobile terrestrial environment with MRC in terms of Average BER of BPSK and BDPSK signaling schemes as a function of SNR are presented in Figures 3-5.

Figure 3 shows the performance of MRC with two signal propagation paths using BPSK signaling scheme. It can be seen that out of 10,000 bits of BPSK signal transmitted at mobile speed of 30 km/h, 3979 bits were erroneous bits in mobile terrestrial environment known as the multipath Rayleigh fading channel, 60 bits were in error in AWGN, while with MRC, the high erroneous bits in mobile terrestrial environment was reduced to 1077 bits all at SNR of 5 dB.

The results obtained were justifiable, in the sense that a bit was used to represent the symbol in the transmission of BPSK. Since the speed of the mobile unit was 30 km/h, the Doppler spread introduced changed the channel condition and caused high errors. The lower Average BER in AWGN was as a result of absence of terrestrial objects which caused multipath.

Figure 4 shows the simulated Average BER of Binary DPSK scheme versus SNR. It was observed that, 704 bits were erroneous in the transmission of 10000 bits Binary DPSK signal with MRC. This is due to the fact that the input binary sequence was first differentially encoded and then modulated using BPSK modulator. The differentially encoded sequence was generated from the input binary sequence by complementing the modulo-2. Figure 5 depicts the simulation of Average BER of BPSK and BDPSK schemes with MRC in mobile terrestrial environment for the purpose of comparison. It was observed that to achieve the same Average BER for BPSK and BDPSK schemes when transmitted the same number of 10000 bits using MRC at the receiver, BPSK needs extra power to achieve the same performance. For example to achieve the same Average BER of 0.07046, BPSK scheme needs extra 4dB. It has been shown from the results that BPSK is not power efficient.

In Figure 6, the received images were plotted at SNR of 12dB, it can be seen from the simulation results that, the received images quality were almost the same as original in AWGN, while in mobile terrestrial environment; the image quality was bad, degraded by random noise and block noise. Figure 7 shows the effect of using MRC to process the received the image data which was modulated with BPSK and BDPSK signaling schemes in mobile terrestrial environment. It was also observed that the image quality was improved but the received image quality of BDPSK was better than BPSK scheme.

Figure3: Simulated Average BER of BPSK scheme versus SNR using MRC

Figure 4: Simulated Average BER of BDPSK scheme versus SNR using MRC

Figure 5: Simulated Average BER of BPSK, BDPK schemes versus SNR using MRC

Modulating image

Mobile terrestrial Environment	With MRC, BPSK scheme	In AWGN

Figure 6: BPSK scheme images received at 30 km/h in different environments

Figure 7: BDPSK scheme images received at 30 km/h in different environments

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the performances of BPSK and BDPSK signaling schemes in mobile terrestrial environment have been evaluated with randomly produced data and image source data. The simulation results show that the performance of BDPSK signaling scheme was found to be better than BPSK scheme giving the lower Average BER i.e. lower erroneous bits were received at the same point when transmitting the same number of bits. Moreover, the received image quality was also in agreement with the performance when randomly produced source data was used. These show practical validation of the simulation results. Therefore, the results presented here through the simulation studies have shown that modulations were very effective in combating fading due to terrestrial environment.

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Z.K. Adeyemo and, T.I. Raji: Continental J. Engineering Sciences 5: (1): 27 - 37, 2010

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Received for Publication: 23/01/10

Accepted for Publication: 12/02/10

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